

ISic0187

I.Sicily inscription 0187

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

porphyry

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Date and context of discovery not recorded; not seen by Gualtherus; Mommsen in CIL states 'apud Petrum Rubeum proconservatorem' and appears to have seen it.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucius) · Iulius · L(uci) · f(ilius) · Quir(ina tribu)

2. Attilianus

3. vix(it) · an(nis) · XIX

4. mens(ibus) · VII · d(iebus) · XIII

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

Lucius Iulius Attilianus, son of Lucius, of the Quirina tribe, lived for 19 years, 7 months, 14 days.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285216

EDR 127388
EDCS 22100116

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7414 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 109

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0187. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334478>